

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OBURA****FIRST NAME: RAPHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401D****COURSE CODE : DIPH****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

Although writing an academic essay is not a linear process, there are certain steps that need to be followed to produce quality academic/scholarly essay. Which of the followings is the most important step in this process.

Analyzing/understanding what the task requires before any other process.¹

Starting the essay writing process early enough.

Having an essay plan.

Not procrastinating the essay writing process.

Which of the following statements is incorrect about the academic essay?

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: (Euclid University 2021, 7).

In the body of the essay, the writer does a brief analysis specific to the point on the topic at hand, structuring the arguments into different paragraphs- that constitute the pillars of the argument.²

An excellent academic essay is structured into three components: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion.

A thesis statement is included in the introduction, preferably in the first paragraph.

In the body of the essay, each paragraph contains a sentence that introduces the main idea, sentences that explain the main idea, and evidence that supports the main idea.

In academic spheres/communities, plagiarism constitutes a serious offense. Which of the following does not constitute plagiarism?

Writing and not citing information that is considered common knowledge.³

Providing in-text citations through paraphrasing and having no reference or bibliographic list.

The writer uses another author's original words in his/her writing without acknowledging that source.

The writer picks information from his/her book/article/journal without acknowledging that source.

² IBID., 10.

³ IBID., 34-37.

1. **The followings are true about critical appraisal of research papers except**

- Sometimes the reason may not be relevant to the claim; in that case, the researcher should anticipate this doubt from the readers and proactively provide an explanation supporting the reason.
- The appraiser assesses how the researcher uses reasons to support his claim.
- The reason is always relevant to the claim, therefore is no need for the researcher to anticipate doubts in the minds of the readers and provide an explanation in advance.⁴**
- The appraiser assesses how the researcher uses evidence to support his/her claim.

Which of the followings is the most crucial consideration in undertaking any research project.?

The researcher's inherent interest in the topic under investigation.⁵

The famous question among the researcher's peers, in which they seek to answer.

The researcher's curiosity.

Whether or not the research question or topic will address practical and conceptual challenges/problems.

2. **Secondary sources of data:**

- Provides data in its original form that supports the testing of the working hypothesis.

⁴ Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press), 19.

⁵ IBID., 23.

- It can be derived from Wikipedia and used in scholarly work.
- Usually derived from articles, and are primarily intended for scholarly and or professional audiences.⁶**
- It targets general audiences.

In searching for data to answer research questions, the researcher examines the sources for reliability and relevancy. Specifically, in the determination of the reliability of the sources, the researcher takes into account all the following except

The Publishing-related costs.⁷

Sources published by reputable presses.

Peer-reviewed sources.

The author's reputation.

The content of online sources mirrors the content of other sources, such as print, but the researcher should take extra care when citing these sources because:

Electronic sources always require additional information to be added such as Uniform Resource Locator (URL) but sometimes URL can disappear- making it hard for the readers to locate the source.⁸

Electronic sources are never authentic.

Readers never trust electronic sources.

The electronic sources are not relevant.

⁶ IBID., 35.

⁷ IBID., 41-42.

⁸ IBID., 141.

In the notes-bibliography style:

The writer appends a subscript number at the close of a sentence he or she quotes, followed by citing the source in a matching-numbered note that provides details of the source referred to in the text.⁹

Footnotes do not allow readers to make instant references.

End notes allow the readers to make instant references.

Reserachers do not number notes chronologically to escape confusion.

3. In conducting a study, the study title is the first statement that the readers interface with. It is, therefore, prudent that the study title communicates to the readers the purpose of the study; To achieve this, the reseracher:

- Ensures that the title is wordy so that the purpose of the study is clearer to the readers.
- Ensures that the readers are not clear on what to expect so that they keep anticipating surprises.
- Includes the type of study, which may be an analysis, and the participants.¹⁰**
- Ensures that the back matter issues are included.

⁹ IBID., 147.

¹⁰Bloomberg, Linda Dale, Volpe. Marie. 2019. Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End. (California: SAGE Publications), 65–66.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, Volpe. Marie. 2019. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. (California: SAGE Publications), 65–66

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.